

Morphological Characteristics of The Paired Fins and Anal Fin of *Oreochromis Mossambicus*

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Abstract:

Oreochromis mossambicus was selected as experimental fish for this manuscript. Fishes were collected from the near by water resources and brought to the laboratory and sacrificed for their pectoral and pelvic fins and their girdles and articulating joints. Photographs were taken. Detailed observations were made in live fish and with the help of photographs taken.

Introduction and Background:

Oreochromis belongs to the Cichlidae family and is also known as Cichlid and is widely distributed in Asian sub-continent, America and African countries. It has very fast growth rate with acclimatization in any waters and can tolerate harsh environmental conditions and salinity¹. There are about 37 species of *Oreochromis* of which *mossambicus* species is bred all over the world specially in the tropical regions like India on account of its very high demand, and it is easy to culture in ponds, rivers and lakes².

It is a native of Africa but was introduced in India in 1952 from the Sri Lanka and Thailand to flourish the fishery industry in India (Jhingran, 1991; Talwar & Jhingran, 1991)³ and ⁴. *Oreochromis* has many characteristics like salinity tolerance, and can thrive in low oxygen concentrations, it can breed in open as well as confined waters, fast growth and adaptation and high fecundity which makes this fish a best fit for aquaculture⁵ (Pillay, 1990).

Methodology:

All basic information about *O. mossambicus* is available but above all these

there is scarcity of information about the paired fins, their structure and their osteology and for this fish species were collected from Narangi minor dam in front of Vinayakrao Patil Mahavidyalaya, Vaijapur and were acclimatized to laboratory conditions by keeping them in a aquarium. Some fishes were studied in live condition while others were sacrificed to study their osteological morphology.

Observations were made in detail, and photographs were taken by Nikon DSLR 5300 from a macro lens of 2.8 aperture to study the morphological characteristics of the fins. in detail.

Result and Discussion:

Of all the paired and unpaired fins, pectoral fins are of most importance as they have various functions as they aid in steering and manoeuvring, downward and upward movement of fish, also it supports in balancing and stability of the fish, sometimes acts as brakes to slow down the movement of the fish, helping maintain orientation and much more but the important ones are steering, balancing and maneuvering⁶.

Paired fins are always supported by girdles like the pectoral girdle supports pectoral

fins and pelvic girdle supports the pelvic fins. The bony structures of the pelvic girdle are the cleithrum, scapula, coracoid, and radials⁷.

The pectoral fins have 13 soft rays (Fig. 1.) which are bifurcated and very slender tube-like hollow. In pectoral fin there are only soft rays which are branched (Fig. 2.) and known as Lepidotrichia which procure the fin flexibility and smooth swift movement⁸.

In *Oreochromis mossambicus*, the pelvic fins exhibit a thoracic placement, corresponding to the condition observed in advanced teleosts, where the fins are positioned beneath or slightly anterior to the pectoral fins. In contrast, primitive teleosts typically possess pelvic fins located more posteriorly in a sub-thoracic position. The thoracic positioning of the pelvic fins in *O. mossambicus* indicates its evolutionary advancement towards the modern teleost condition (Fig. 3)⁹.

The examination of the pelvic fin revealed the presence of a single hard spine accompanied by five soft rays (Fig. 4), consistent with the findings reported by Lagler *et al.* (1977)¹⁰. The principal soft rays are robust and broadened at the fin base, extending to approximately half its total length before bifurcating at the mid-region. A total of 32 bifurcated soft rays were observed, tapering distally, with their free ends extending beyond the integument covering the pelvic fin (Fig. 4).

The pelvic fins primarily function to maintain the stability of the fish during locomotion, enabling it to swim in an upright position and preventing lateral rolling or inversion. Additionally, these fins play a crucial role in braking and modulating swimming velocity during directional changes (Nelson *et al.*, 2016).

The anal fin, a single median structure located ventrally along the midline of the body, is

positioned posterior to the cloacal opening and anterior to the caudal fin or the commencement of the tail region (Fig. 3). Similar structural observations were reported by Nelson *et al.* (2016).

Morphologically, the anal fin of *O. mossambicus* possesses three distinct spines—one short (approximately 1 cm), one intermediate (2 cm), and one long (3.5 cm)—along with nine primary soft rays. Each primary soft ray bifurcates into two secondary branches at approximately mid-length, and these secondary branches further bifurcate into tertiary branches. The terminal ends of these tertiary rays are pointed, totaling 36 in number, and extend beyond the epidermal membrane enveloping the anal fin (Fig. 5).

Conclusions:

Studies and literature are available on fins of fishes but more emphasis must be placed on the bony structures that support the fins, mainly the girdles, pectoral and pelvic girdle and the spine.

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Fig. 1. Pectoral fin

Fig. 2. Pectoral fin rays

Fig. 3. DF – Dorsal fin; PF-Pectoral fin; PLF – Pelvic fin; AF – Anal fin

Fig. 4. Pelvic fin

Fig. 5. Anal fin: FS- First Spine; SS – Second spine; TS – Third spine; BSR – Bifurcated soft rays

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